

Original Research Article

Female Objectification, Insensitivity and Performative Aggression in an Online Contemporary Comedy Show *India's Got Latent*

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the intersection of misogyny, sexist humour and accountability in comedy content in India through a content analysis of the controversial show *India's Got Latent* season 1. Comedy in India has historically served as a medium for social commentary, yet it often gets embroiled in controversies for sexist and misogynist content. This paper traces how comedic content creators of stand-up comedy shows garner laughs and applause from the audience by normalizing crude humour and female objectification. Taking the case study of select episodes of the comedy show *India's Got Latent* season 1, this paper examines how the show exploited topics on sexuality, insensitivity and performative aggression to garner audience laughs. The analysis reveals the tension between creative freedom and societal norms, raising critical questions about the ethical responsibilities of comedians and the liberal approach of accepting humour in the Indian context. It is identified that stand-up comedy shows are cruder than the traditional comedy or humour around female objectification in films and television, as it engages the crowd in laughing as a spectacle for reinforcing the normalizing of hostile sexism. These comedy shows position women's bodies as objects of comedic spectacle, consequently framing insensitivity and performative aggression disguised as humour in a display of hostile sexism.

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Introduction

Comedy has been historically functioning as a mirror to the society often reflecting and reinforcing prevailing social norms, hierarchies, and power relations. While humour is often framed as innocuous entertainment but scholars across multiple disciplines have challenged this assumption arguing that comedic content in broadcast and streaming television can serve

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as a potent vehicle for ideological reproduction (Lockyer & Pickering, 2009). Further, the most persistently examined concerns is the manner in which women are depicted in comedy shows as objects of ridicule, sexual spectacle, or targets of aggressive comedic acts (Gill, 2007).

A stand-up comedy show is “a show of embellished laughters or a setup of monologic paradigm, which inculcate the perpetual ideas of shared humour, as well as spontaneous conversational jokes” (Sidique, 2024, January 25). In India, stand-up comedy shows have become an integral part of entertainment and have been witnessing a boom despite challenges (Kohli-Khandekar, 2025, December 29). It provides comedians to comment on social issues, politics, culture, and other dynamics. In India, Indian television has seen a variety of comedy shows like *The Great Indian Laughter Challenge*, which was the first stand-up comedy show. Then many shows like *Comedy ke superstars*, *Laugh India Laugh*, *Comedy open mic* and *The Kapil Sharma show* have reached a large number of audiences (Kumar 2003).

The first season of *India's Got Latent* was also launched on 14th June 2024, by Samay Raina on his YouTube channel, an India's Got Latent app on iOS and Android (Sanzgiri, 2024, June 25). However, soon the show got embroiled in a controversy due to misogynist and controversial comments of a fellow stand-up comedian during one of the episodes landing the show host Raina facing summons from the Maharashtra Cyber Department (Tripathi, 2025, February 12). Soon the show stopped and episodes were made private in YouTube on February 12, 2025 (Tripathi, 2025, February 12). In the past, other comedy shows have exploited sexist humour like the AIB knockout show hosted by Karan Johar got censored for using vulgar jokes and sexual reference (Al Jazeera, 2015).

However, in June 2026, the stand-up comedy show *India's Got Latent* season 2 once again began streaming simultaneously on Netflix and YouTube (Indian Television, 2026, June 22). Though many comedy shows have been banned or censored in India for several reasons, it initiates a debate about creative freedom and cultural sensitivity, pushing the boundaries of normalisation (HT News Desk, 2025, February 11; Sidique, 2024, January 25, *Telangana Today*, 2026, June 11). With the constant scrutiny of entertainment content and social media policing, comedy, which once acted as a mirror to the society, faces constant censorship by both the audience and government (Tripathi, 2025, February 12; Sanzgiri, 2024, June 25; Ahmad et al, 2025). Kumar et al (2023) argue that since audiences increasingly prefer such content over clean humour, social media too reflects this shift, with vulgar meme pages like *Adult Gram*, *Qtiyapa*, and *Tharki Society* amassing millions of followers. Similarly, popular Indian television shows such as *Bhabiji Ghar Par Hain*, *Happu ki Ultan Paltan*, and *Comedy*

Nights with Kapil feature adult-oriented humour and sexual comments (Shukla, 2022, January 13).

Theoretical Framework

Fredrickson and Roberts (1997) posit that female objectification refers to the treatment of women as instruments for others' visual pleasure or comedic utility, reducing their personhood to physical attributes. Hence, the Objectification theory provides a foundational framework for understanding how media systematically positions women as bodies to be evaluated (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). The theory posits that repeated exposure to sexually objectifying media fosters self-objectification in female viewers and normalises the objectifying gaze in male viewers. Applied to comedy, the framework reveals how comedic formats sitcoms, sketch comedy, late-night shows structurally rely on the female body as a prop or punchline (Reichert & Lambiase, 2003). In this context we also identify how insensitivity in the content of comedy shows normalises these callousness toward the suffering, dignity, or social position of women through repeated comedic framing (Billig, 2005). Lockyer and Pickering (2009) theorised insensitivity as a structural feature of transgressive or "offensive" comedy, arguing that comedians and producers often invoke freedom of expression and the cathartic function of humour to justify content that systematically demeans marginalised groups. In their analysis, insensitivity is not an accident of poor taste but a deliberate comedic register that signals social transgression and in-group belonging for audiences who share the joke's ideological premises.

Performative aggression denotes the enactment of hostile or demeaning behaviour in verbal, physical, or symbolic as a theatrical display within comedic contexts, often directed at women and justified under the guise of humour (Cowan & O'Brien, 1990). Further, this paper also draws from the Superiority Theory (Hobbes, 1651/1994) of humour to relate how laughter arises from a sense of superiority over the subject of the joke. This theory is particularly relevant to understanding performative aggression when comedic acts target women by their appearance, intelligence, sexuality, or social aspirations where the audience is invited to position itself above the female subject, deriving pleasure from her humiliation (Billig, 2005). This dynamic naturalises hierarchies of gender and sustains insensitivity toward women's experiences. Performative aggression refers to acts of hostility, humiliation, or dominance that are enacted as theatrical display within a comedic context, with the laughter of an audience serving as both validation and legitimation of the aggressive act (Cowan & O'Brien, 1990). Regardless of form, the defining characteristic is that the aggression is performed for an audience that is expected to find it amusing (Weaver et al., 2016).

Review of Literature

The existing critical attention focuses on stand-up comedy and identity via analysis of a single axis of identity, such as race (Weaver, 2011; Pérez, 2022), gender (Lockyer, 2011; Pérez and Greene, 2016), social class (Friedman, 2014) or disability (Lockyer, 2015) and intersectional analysis of stand-up comedy (Huc-Hepher, 2021; Pickette, 2022). James (2019, p.831) argues that stand-up comedy creates representation of the city of Mumbai as a “safe” space for the new middle-class women, excluding Dalit and working-class, deemed “dangerous.” Further, James (2019) notes that this is materialized by mobilising places and infrastructure that identify Mumbai as a world-class city, and simultaneously appropriating gender hierarchies in the pursuit of Indianness. Another study by Sarkar and Siraj (2022, p.41) demonstrate how ideology and identity constructions are simultaneously represented and reinforced through the same comic moment witnessing an “increase in the use of rape humour in Indian stand-up comedy”. Finally, the extracted portion of recorded performances shows that the whole event unfolds as an informal, naturally developing encounter between audience and comedian.

Banerjee and Kumar (2024) also conducted a critical discourse analysis of videos of stand-up comedy uploaded on YouTube of Indian stand-up comedians, to identify the nature and use of profanity. It was identified that Indian comedians purposefully incorporated Hindi and English profanity into their stand-up acts to enhance the comedic impact of their act (Banerjee & Kumar, 2024). Further, it was found that profanity plays an integral role and relevance in Indian stand-up comedy discourses (Banerjee & Kumar, 2024).

Much of the existing critical attention focuses on mostly on western comedy shows and those in Indian context are yet to receive sustained attention. This paper will hence, engage with the representation of objectification, insensitivity, performative aggression in the standup comedy discourse by analyzing how such events or shows navigate boundaries of comedy and social taboo in India. This paper investigates i) Which type of content or themes in *India's Got Latent* commonly led the show to public controversy? ii) How did the judges or performers engage to normalise sensitive or offensive jokes? And iii) What kind of content in the show qualifies for performative aggression?

Methodology and analysis

For this study mixed method content analysis has been adopted, both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The qualitative approach includes the observation of 10 episodes of India's Got Latent (7 regular and 3 bonus episodes) of total 18 episodes. This will include

identifying the context, nature, and elements of jokes behind censorship or self-censorship in the performances. This analysis gives an understanding of how comedians navigate sensitive topics such as religion, caste, politics, and social taboos etc. This method is appropriate for interpreting the nature of jokes and implications of censored content beyond frequency counts. The quantitative component systematically coded the presence or absence of elements of jokes which may be vulgar and cause censorship in the episodes using a binary coding system (1 for presence, 0 for absence). Each episode was analyzed for the frequency, patterns and varieties of elements used in jokes by the performers or judges in the show (like sexist, gender biased, regional, language etc).

Table 1. Variable and operational definitions

Variables	Operationalization
	<i>Objectification</i>
Sexual reference	Remarks involving sexual activity, pornography, objectification of individuals based on gender identity
Misogynism	Jokes reinforcing negative stereotypes about women, belittling their economic opportunities, or political representation
	<i>Performative aggression</i>
Offensive language	Use of offensive language and regional slangs by performers and judges
Body-shaming reference	Humor targeting a person's physical appearance or attributes derogatorily
	<i>Insensitivity</i>
Disability	Making fun of someone's disability for humor ²⁴
Cultural reference	Jokes about rituals, practices of any community

Source: Authors

By combining qualitative and quantitative content analysis, this mixed-method approach provided both the depth of understanding and the breadth of measurement necessary to explore the elements and themes of jokes to be censored. The qualitative methods helped to contextualize and explain the quantitative findings, while the quantitative data will offer a structured overview of the pattern of comedy.

We analysed ten (n=10) episodes of the Indian comedy show *India's Got Latent*, consisting of seven regular episodes and three bonus episodes. The regular episodes selected are odd-numbered episodes 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, and episode 12 while the out of the total six bonus episodes, three even-numbered episodes 2, 4, and 6 were selected for this study. This systematic selection was made to avoid biases in the sample selection of the researchers. The episodes being were watched multiple times separately by the authors and coded using a code sheet and consequently reaching agreement in all of them. The codes operationalized for the study have been presented in Table 1 above.

Results and Findings

The analysis of the study reveals patterns of comedy that may violate boundaries of acceptance in India. The format, language, themes contribute to bring attention towards the show garnering more virality and revenue. The analysis also identifies a template of offensive language exploited in this show to nudge the audience into group acceptance of rape myths, aggression, gender insensitivity and sexism.

Prevalence of Sexually Explicit Jokes:

Jokes on child marriage and paedophilia were used in the text of the show casually detaching the crudeness and misogyny from it. The audiences and the judges made a spectacle of loud applause and laughter post each of these deliveries that coaxed the viewers into accepting such language and explicit references as normal, which should otherwise have been noted as deeply offensive. In episodes 5 and 7 of *India's Got Latent*, significant amount of provocative content were catered to the audiences, often presenting use of vulgar and sexist language, without muting or hiding the sound. One of these jokes involved a guitarist, referring to his fingering of guitar strings to a sexual innuendo, portraying the use of wordplay to introduce adult themes.

Additionally, jokes were made referring "body count," a term used to imply the number of past sexual partners. In one segment, a female participant was asked her "body count," which was presented humorously but carried undertones of objectification. Female performers were often criticized for their outfits, appearance, and personal relationships. Jokes about "body count" or comments like "looks matter..." have been significantly presented in all the episodes analysed for this study.

Further, like other episodes under study, we find the continued the use of provocative humour, sexual innuendos, and controversial political commentary in episode 9. In this episode, both the judges and the performers made explicit jokes involving body size, sexual practices, and

abortion. It was also found that almost all the episodes under study included jokes about sexual practices, pornography, details about physical intimacy, delivering adult content casually.

Performative Aggression, Use of Vulgar and Offensive Language:

Performers and judges frequently used vulgar words and regional slang, which are usually considered offensive, but are passed on as casual references, demeaning women, sexual minorities and other communities. While the first episode started with a controlled tone and light performances, the show gathered momentum in viewership with increased use of performative aggression in its later episodes. It was noticed that the judges and the performers in the show were at par in abusing obscene language and aggressive tones during the show to elicit comedic relief from the audience. However, some incidents or remarks highlighted vulgar words or slang, mostly used by the judges. One of the episodes concluded with a heated exchange between two judges, Deepak Kalal and Puneet Superstar, who abused each other, targeting each other's families, financial conditions, and social status in vulgar language using slang. While framed humorously, this interaction underscored the performative aggression and sensationalism central to the show's format highlighting the shows reliance on provocative moments for popularity and viewership.

Use of references like a performer mentioning in his description that he was a "mommy lover", making it an explicit indication of sexual preferences. These antics were repeatedly exploited to draw audience attention to the show, igniting a debate on the use of objectification and misogyny to create a buzz around the show. While the audience and the panel of judges laughed at these references, sometimes indicating their double-meaning references, the language and content of the show could not be ignored in a deeply patriarchal and misogynistic society that could do more harm than entertaining the audience.

Additionally, during the conversations among the judges, they used explicit Hindi slangs, the terms that are considered as offensive in public discourse. The usage of such language by the panel itself demonstrates a casual normalisation of this kind of vulgarity in comedy shows. A rap performance in one of the episodes under study was replete with offensive language, where the performer used many offensive words in the lyrical composition, employing vulgarity as a variety to evoke reaction. Some of the episodes like the one in episode 3 had one performer also share his sex life. Rather than avoiding or censoring such topics in the show, the judges teased him playfully, bringing our humorous reactions from the audiences. This reinforced how the comedy show uses humour to normalize topics which are often considered as sensitive

in Indian society. Overall, this episode highlighted the liberal approach to adult content, reflecting shifting standards of the audiences of Indian comedy shows.

Mockery of Sensitive Social Issues, Religious and Cultural References:

Issues like child marriage, disability, caste, and poverty were used as topics for eliciting laughter, often seen as unintentional, reinforcing negative stereotypes that did more harm than the humour. Some jokes were made based on religious or cultural rituals, which may be offensive to certain communities. One of the most significant performances came from Bhavya Shah, a blind stand-up comedian, who using his disability as a tool for satire, delivered a bold social commentary. He stated, “My life is like Kashmir, always blackout,” directly narrating to the political situation in Kashmir. Bhavya also made a joke about racism, stating he could not be racist because he could not see, which highlighted social biases using irony. But ironically when a differently-abled performer entered the stage for a stand-up comedy act, Samay Raina called it “sit-down comedy”, turning his disability into a joke. Overall, the episodes continued using dark humour, sexual jokes, and insensitive comments about sensitive issues like disability, homosexuality, and child marriage.

Conclusion

The show *India's Got Latent* reveals a significant shift in the boundaries of acceptable comedy in India, where humour including sexuality, politics, vulgarity, and social taboos is significantly being normalized. The show, featuring uncensored performances and judge commentary, often included jokes on sensitive themes such as pornography, child marriage, dowry, etc. The maximum of this performance was met with laughter from both the audience and the judge panel, which raises critical concerns about the role of censorship in shaping ethical standards for public broadcasting.

Controversy regarding this show led judge Samay Raina to self-censor and make the videos private in YouTube, illustrating the tension between comedic freedom and public accountability. The use of offensive slang, sexual innuendo, and provocative commentary may not always violate formal censorship rules, but it can challenge societal norms.

The show *India's Got Latent* raises a concern about the evolving discourse on comedy and censorship in India. While it reflects the growing liberalism around digital platforms among Indians, it also suggests that comedians too, like other media producers, have to abide by certain ethical norms regarding the social context and sensitivity. The performative dimension is crucial where the presence of an audience transforms what might otherwise be understood as

straightforward aggression into a social ritual in which aggression is aestheticised, commodified, and applauded. In comedy shows, performative aggression takes multiple forms such as verbal aggression, through insults, mockery, and demeaning commentary on physical aggression through slapstick directed at female characters where relational aggression through public humiliation and social exclusion and sexual aggression through non-consensual touching, unwanted flirtation, and the comedic framing of harassment as flattery or seduction.

The rise of digital media and OTT Platforms has transformed comedy consumption, where algorithms often reward controversial and sensational content because it generates more clicks, and engagement leading to revenue. This shock value becomes commercially profitable consequently rewarding the comedians who escalate vulgarity to remain relevant. Further, audiences become habituated to extreme content and these vulgarity, objectification and insensitivity becomes normalized in online media discourses unlike the traditional legacy media. The repeated exposure to these contents creates a risk of influence on young minds. Repetition and humour lowers the sensitivity and critical resistance of audiences towards such overt representation of misogyny and hostile sexism. Further, the group laughter and comedic response paves the path for social acceptance of such insensitive content. It is recommended that these shows should avoid hate speech and dehumanization of the participants as well as the minorities and sensitive issues. Satire should be clearly distinguished from harassment to maintain a balance between freedom of speech and expression with social awareness.

Obscenity and vulgarity in comedy shows do not automatically ruin the morality of audiences, but excessive dependence on crude humour might influence social behaviour, language, and cultural sensitivity over time. The impact varies according to audience maturity, social environment, intent of the comedian, and media exposure. Comedy can entertain, criticize society, and promote free expression, but, when vulgarity becomes a primary source of humour, it risks normalizing disrespect, insensitivity, and shallow entertainment culture. The real challenge is therefore not simply banning offensive comedy, but encouraging ethical creativity, responsible media consumption, and stronger moral education within society.

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